

STI2022
GRANADA | SEP 7+8+9

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators
"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

#STI2022GRX

Full paper

STI 2022 Conference Proceedings

Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators

All papers published in this conference proceedings have been peer reviewed through a peer review process administered by the proceedings Editors. Reviews were conducted by expert referees to the professional and scientific standards expected of a conference proceedings.

Proceeding Editors

Nicolas Robinson-Garcia
Daniel Torres-Salinas
Wenceslao Arroyo-Machado

Citation: Ghiasi, G., Tajmel, T., & Larivière, V. (2022). Gender homophily in patent examinations. In N. Robinson-Garcia, D. Torres-Salinas, & W. Arroyo-Machado (Eds.), *26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators*, STI 2022 (sti22205). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6948295>

Copyright: © 2022 the authors, © 2022 Faculty of Communication and Documentation, University of Granada, Spain. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#).

Collection: <https://zenodo.org/communities/sti2022grx/>

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators | STI 2022

“From Global Indicators to Local Applications”

7-9 September 2022 | Granada, Spain

#STI22GRX

Gender homophily in patent examinations

Gita Ghiasi*, Tanja Tajmel**, Vincent Larivière*

*gita.ghiasi.hafezi@umontreal.ca; vincent.lariviere@umontreal.ca

École de bibliothéconomie et des sciences de l'information, Université de Montréal, C.P. 6128, Succ. Centre-Ville, Montréal, QC, H3C 3J7 (Canada)

**tanja.tajmel@concordia.ca

Centre for Engineering in Society, Concordia University, 1455 De Maisonneuve Blvd. W., Montréal, QC, H3G 1M8 (Canada)

Introduction

The shift of innovation policies toward the direct involvement of research and development in economic development has been extensively reflected in the emphasis on patenting. Patenting measures are often tied to commercial success and are increasingly used to evaluate innovative performance (Hagedoorn and Cloudt 2003) and hence are rewarding in technological fields.

These rewards span from monetary gains to visibility, reputation and prestige (Göktepe-Hulten and Mahagaonkar 2010). Patents are sometimes rewarded more than publications (Keller 1997). This is because involvement in innovation and commercialization is connected with both social power and occupational success (Meng 2017). Therefore, patenting measures can serve as a guide for employee recruitment and promotion and, most notably, employee retention (Ganco et al. 2015; Ge et al. 2016).

However, on the one hand, the use of patenting as a convenient measure of innovation could not precipitate economic growth (Iwaisako and Futagami 2013), and on the other hand, sustainable economic development cannot take root unless accompanied by an enabling of socio-economic context for inclusive growth. Patenting is characterized as a highly male-dominated activity: women's patenting rate was only 10.8% in 2013 (Sugimoto et al. 2015).

The patenting gender gap is persistent in Japan (Ashcraft and Breitzman 2007), the European Union (EU) (Kugele 2010), and specific European countries (Ejermeo and Jung 2012; Frietsch et al. 2009; Mauleón et al. 2014; Mauleón and Bordons 2009; Naldi et al. 2004). Women's patents are less likely to be granted or to be maintained (Jensen et al. 2018). Even if granted, women's patents receive lower citation rates than those of men (Jensen et al. 2018; Sugimoto et al. 2015). These gender differences have not only important implications for the dissemination and production of technical knowledge at full capacity but also present consequences for the hiring, promotion, and retention of women in science and technology (S&T) sectors and could impair women's career progression.

This gender gap is often attributed to the dearth of women in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) fields. However, this has been contested by Hunt et al. (2013), who showed that “only 7% of the gap in patenting rates is accounted for by women’s lower probability of holding any science or engineering degree, because women with such a degree are scarcely more likely to patent than women without” (p. 831). Other explanations include but are not limited to organizational structure, gender differences in networking opportunities (Whittington and Smith-Doerr 2008), lack of exposure to commercial activities (Ding et al. 2006), lower collaboration with industry (Tartari and Salter 2015), lack of mentoring and institutional support for women, and a lower rate of women’s appointment to high profile administrative positions (Murray and Graham 2007), gender differences in attitudes towards risk, competition, scientific commercialization, involvement in a different type of research, efforts in balancing work and personal life, gendered preferences of venture capitalists, and gender discounting (Stephan and El-Ganainy 2007).

Along these lines, gendered practices in the patent examination could also contribute to the gender disparities in patenting. It has been shown that patent examiners are more likely to reject or reduce the scope and value of patents filed by women (Jensen et al. 2018). A patent attorney or agent plays an important role in the examination process as well, as these licensed experts prepare and file patent applications and represent inventors before the USPTO. When a representative is appointed, further communications happen in the form of correspondence between the Office and the attorney(s) or agent(s). This study sheds light on these practices and presents gender differences in the patent examination process in different sectors and technical fields.

RQ1. Is the gender of the patent examiner and attorney(s) associated with the proportion of women listed as inventors on the patent when we control the number of claims, figures and drawings, collaboration and innovation types?

RQ2. Do these patterns change across technological fields and sectors?

RQ3. Is the gender of the examiner, attorney(s) and inventor(s) of a patent related to the length of the patent granting period?

For this purpose, this paper provides a comprehensive analysis of granted utility patents to scrutinize differences in female inventorship and processing time of patents granted by female and male examiners and represented by female and male attorneys.

Data and Methods

This study examines 6,299,230 utility patents from 1976 to 2020 granted by the United States Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO). Gender is assigned to inventors, examiners and representatives in a similar approach as introduced in (Larivière et al. 2013; Sugimoto et al. 2015) using universal and country-specific existing name and gender databases, including GenderChecker¹, U.S. Census, WikiName, Wikipedia, France and Quebec lists, and country-specific lists. The contribution from female inventors to a patent or ‘*female inventorship*’ is measured as a fractional count of female inventors (the number of female inventors divided by the number of co-inventors of a patent to which gender is attributed). Similarly, the dominant gender of a patent is considered as female ‘F’ when share of female inventorship is larger than 55% and as male ‘M’ when female inventorship is lower than 45%. It is considered as balanced ‘B’ when it is between 45% and 55%.

¹ GenderChecker is a name and gender database developed based on 2001 and 2011 UK Census and multiple online sources and contributions. This database assigns only one gender to a name and in cases where a name appears as both male and female (even for one instance), the gender is assigned as Unisex.

Collaborations are defined based on the country and city of inventors. In this study, regional collaboration refers to those collaborations in which all inventors are from one city, and interregional collaboration refers to those granted to inventors located in different cities of one country. Similarly, open innovation in this study is defined when a patent is granted to at least two different assignees and is considered international when assignees are not from the same country.

The application processing time (or application length) of a patent is defined as the number of *months* between the patent's application and the issue date. Applications refer to requests for protection of inventions, whereas granted (or issued ones) are those patents that have not been rejected or withdrawn. The processing time is further normalized by the granted year and the technological field. Patent citation data in this study is limited to the citing USPTO patents and is also normalized by the granted year and the technological field.

Patent claims are numbered expressions that define the scope of protection afforded by the patent. The number of claims is often associated with the quality of patents because it reflects both the technological breadth of a patent and its expected market value (Lanjouw and Schankerman 2004; Squicciarini et al. 2013). We also included the number of figures and drawings to consider patent characteristics more comprehensively.

Since patent claims follow skewed distributions, boxplot analysis is utilized to eliminate outliers. In this analysis, outliers are defined as values greater than the third quartile (Q3) by at least 1.5 times the interquartile range (IQR). Therefore, the upper whisker for claims is 38 ($20 + 1.5 * (20 - 8)$). A similar approach applies to the number of figures and drawings, for which the upper whisker is 29 and 20.5, respectively. 95% confidence intervals of means are considered to highlight the estimations and provide robust comparisons and are shown in lighter colors in the figures of this study.

Technological fields are assigned based on international classification codes (IPCs)² created by the World Intellectual Property Office (WIPO) and assigned to each patent. In this study, technological fields and subfields are based on eight sections and twenty-two subsection titles. Assignees are further categorized into government, industry, and individual sectors using the USPTO PatentsView's³ assignee type and assignees associated with the university sector are further identified using the keyword filters introduced in Ghiasi & Larivière (2015). Table 1 presents the number of analyzed patents in each field and sector category.

Table 1- Number of patents and share of female-examined per discipline and sector over the period 1976-2020

IPC	IPC Description	Patents	(%F-examined)	Sector	Patents	(%F-examined)
A	Human necessities	1,021,478	24%	Government	54,891	15%
B	Performing operations; transporting	1,215,859	17%	Individual	48,614	16%
C	Chemistry; metallurgy	824,452	28%	Industry	5,421,104	20%
D	Textiles; paper	69,773	14%	University	169,447	29%
E	Fixed constructions	203,888	16%			

² http://www.wipo.int/export/sites/www/classifications/ipc/en/guide/guide_ipc.pdf

³ http://www.patentsview.org/querydev/query/data_dictionary.html

F	Mechanical engineering; lighting; heating; weapons; blasting	606,103	14%
G	Physics	1,921,319	20%
H	Electricity	1,695,451	21%

Results

The number of female-examined patents is increasing over time, and they form 19% of the total granted patents (Fig 1a). The female contribution is higher for patents that are evaluated by a female examiner (Fig 1b). Overall, female inventorship is 3.4% lower for male-examined patents in comparison to female-examined patents. This finding provides a strong implication for gender disparities in inventorship. This is a sizable difference given that women only account for 11% of total inventorship, and 81% of granted patents are examined by men. As Fig 2 shows, this gap is not related to patent characteristics as it still exists when controlling for the year of patent grant (Fig 1b), the number of claims (Fig 2a), figures (Fig 2b), and drawings (Fig 2c).

Figure 1- (a) Share (left axis) and number (right axis) of female-examined patents over time; (b) share of female inventorship over time by examiner’s gender

Figure 2- Share of female inventorship by examiner’s gender when controlling for the numbers of (a) claims, (b) figures and (c) drawings

A similar trend is found when controlling for collaboration types. A lower share of female inventors is found for male-examined inventions induced by international and national (regional and interregional) collaborations, sole inventorship and open innovations (Fig 3). The highest share of female inventorship is observed when inventors are from the same city (here referred to as regional collaborations) (Fig 3a). However, when a patent is filed with a collaboration of another assignee (here referred to as open innovation), the share of female inventorship is higher and is the highest when the two entities are from different countries (Fig 3b).

Figure 3- Share of female inventorship by (a) collaboration type and examiner’s gender; and (b) by innovation type

The results are consistent across the sector(s) of a patent’s assignee(s) and technological fields (IPC sections) (Fig 4). The share of female inventorship is higher when the examiner is a woman across all technological fields and sectors of the assignee(s). This share is the highest when a patent is filed by a university or related to the field of ‘human necessities’ and is examined by a woman.

Figure 4- Share of female inventorship by (a) sector of the assignee and (b) technological field.

The results show that patent inventorships that are represented by a man and examined by a man are also highly male-dominated. On the other hand, the share of female inventorship is higher for those patents represented by women and examined by women.

Figure 5- Share of female inventorship by gender of representative(s) and patent examiner

Our results reveal that when a patent is examined by a woman, the average number of claims is highest for a patent, noting that examiners are often directly involved in drafting patent claims (Fig 6a). However, the citation impact of the patent is lower when the examiner is a woman (Fig 6b). Considering that citation impact and number of claims are highly correlated, these results are important as they reveal implications for gendered practices in citations.

Figure 6-(a) average patent claims (b) relative citations by examiner gender and dominant gender of inventors

When looking into the processing time of the patent, our findings show that if the examiner is a woman, the processing time is longer regardless of the gender of the representative(s) or inventor(s) (Fig 7). However, when the dominant gender on the patent byline is female and the representative is a woman, the processing time is the shortest (Fig 7b).

Figure 7- (a) Relative processing time by dominant gender of patent inventors, and gender of patent examiner, and (b) gender of representative(s)

Discussion and conclusion

This paper is one of the first attempts that sheds light on the gendered practices in the patent examination process. The findings reveal the share of female examiners and female inventors has increased over time but is still considerably low. Along these lines, when the patent examiner is a woman, the granted patent comprises a higher contribution of women inventors. These results are persistent when controlling for patent characteristics, collaboration type, sectors, and technological fields. Moreover, the processing time is longer when the examiner is a woman. This raises the question of whether female examiners' requisitions might be more challenged by the patent representative(s) and inventors (of whom the majority are men) than those of male examiners; or of whether male examiners favor patents with a higher share of male inventors involved.

Along these lines, patent attorneys/agents play a significant role in the examination process, as these are who represent the inventors and are in direct communication with the patent examiners. This paper highlights that in all the sectors and fields, the lowest share of female inventorship is associated with patents represented by male attorney(s) or agent(s) to a male examiner. The opposite of this trend is also applicable to female-examined patents, which contributes to addressing the latter question and suggests the likely presence of gender homophily in the patent examination process.

Patent claims and patent citations are two measures of technological applicability and impact. These two measures are correlated. Interestingly, the average number of claims is higher for female-examined patents, while the citation impact of the patents is lower. This finding, combined with the fact that women receive lower citation rates for their patents, presents an important implication for gendered practices in citations in patents. These practices could induce stark imbalances in gender and inclusion in patenting, as male examiners are responsible for 81% of total patents granted in the USPTO.

This study also sheds light on the importance of open innovation and collaborative entities in addressing gender disparities in patenting, as women are shown to be more involved in patents granted to more than one entity. This study brings forth one of the possible elucidations for gender differences in inventorship and calls for gender-responsive policy mechanisms to provide women an environment conducive to more patenting engagement.

References

- Ashcraft, C., & Breitzman, A. (2007). Who invents IT? An analysis of women's participation in information technology patenting. *National Center for Women & IT*.
- Ding, W. W., Murray, F., & Stuart, T. E. (2006). Gender differences in patenting in the academic life sciences. *Science*, *313*(5787), 665–667.
- Ejermo, O., & Jung, T. (2012). *Demographic patterns and trends in patenting: Gender, age, and education of inventors*. Lund University, CIRCLE-Center for Innovation, Research and Competences in the Learning Economy.
- Frietsch, R., Haller, I., Funken-Vrohlings, M., & Grupp, H. (2009). Gender-specific patterns in patenting and publishing. *Research Policy*, *38*(4), 590–599.
- Ganco, M., Ziedonis, R. H., & Agarwal, R. (2015). More stars stay, but the brightest ones still leave: Job hopping in the shadow of patent enforcement. *Strategic Management Journal*, *36*(5), 659–685. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.2239>
- Ge, C., Huang, K.-W., & Png, I. P. L. (2016). Engineer/scientist careers: Patents, online profiles, and misclassification bias: Online Career Profiles and Misclassification. *Strategic Management Journal*, *37*(1), 232–253. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.2460>
- Ghiasi, G., & Larivière, V. (2015). Sectoral systems of innovation: the case of robotics research activities. *Scientometrics*, *104*(2), 407–424. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-015-1611-9>
- Göktepe-Hulten, D., & Mahagaonkar, P. (2010). Inventing and patenting activities of scientists: in the expectation of money or reputation? *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, *35*(4), 401–423. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-009-9126-2>
- Hagedoorn, J., & Cloudt, M. (2003). Measuring innovative performance: is there an advantage in using multiple indicators? *Research Policy*, *32*(8), 1365–1379. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333\(02\)00137-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333(02)00137-3)
- Iwaisako, T., & Futagami, K. (2013). Patent protection, capital accumulation, and economic growth. *Economic Theory*, *52*(2), 631–668. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00199-011-0658-y>
- Jensen, K., Kovács, B., & Sorenson, O. (2018). Gender differences in obtaining and maintaining patent rights. *Nature Biotechnology*, *36*, 307–309. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt.4120>
- Keller, R. T. (1997). Job involvement and organizational commitment as longitudinal predictors of job performance: A study of scientists and engineers. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, *82*(4), 539.
- Kugele, K. (2010). Chapter 7 Analysis of women's participation in high-technology patenting. In *Innovating Women: Contributions to Technological Advancement* (Vols. 1-0, Vol. 1, pp. 123–151). Emerald Group Publishing Limited. [https://doi.org/10.1108/S2040-7246\(2010\)0000001012](https://doi.org/10.1108/S2040-7246(2010)0000001012)

- Lanjouw, J. O., & Schankerman, M. (2004). Patent Quality and Research Productivity: Measuring Innovation with Multiple Indicators*. *The Economic Journal*, 114(495), 441–465. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0297.2004.00216.x>
- Larivière, V., Ni, C., Gingras, Y., Cronin, B., & Sugimoto, C. R. (2013). Bibliometrics: Global gender disparities in science. *Nature*, 504(7479), 211–213. <https://doi.org/10.1038/504211a>
- Mauleón, E., & Bordons, M. (2009). Male and female involvement in patenting activity in Spain. *Scientometrics*, 83(3), 605–621.
- Mauleón, E., Daraio, C., & Bordons, M. (2014). Exploring gender differences in patenting in Spain. *Research Evaluation*, 23(1), 62–78. <https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvt030>
- Meng, Y. (2017). Gender distinctions in patenting: Does nanotechnology make a difference? *Scientometrics*, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-017-2607-4>
- Murray, F., & Graham, L. (2007). Buying science and selling science: gender differences in the market for commercial science. *Industrial and Corporate Change*, 16(4), 657–689.
- Naldi, F., Luzzi, D., Valente, A., & Parenti, I. V. (2004). Scientific and technological performance by gender. In *Handbook of quantitative science and technology research* (pp. 299–314). Springer. http://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/1-4020-2755-9_14. Accessed 19 June 2014
- Squicciarini, M., Dernis, H., & Criscuolo, C. (2013). Measuring patent quality.
- Stephan, P. E., & El-Ganainy, A. (2007). The entrepreneurial puzzle: explaining the gender gap. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 32(5), 475–487.
- Sugimoto, C. R., Ni, C., West, J. D., & Larivière, V. (2015). The Academic Advantage: Gender Disparities in Patenting. *PLOS ONE*, 10(5), e0128000. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0128000>
- Tartari, V., & Salter, A. (2015). The engagement gap:: Exploring gender differences in University–Industry collaboration activities. *Research Policy*, 44(6), 1176–1191.
- Whittington, K. B., & Smith-Doerr, L. (2008). Women inventors in context: Disparities in patenting across academia and industry. *Gender & Society*, 22(2), 194–218.